

Certification Protocol for Integrated Interventions “Historical Small Smart Cities”: An Instrument for the Sustainable Regeneration of Minor Historical Centers

Valentina Pica

Roma Tre University, Italy

ABSTRACT

This paper presents an environmental and cultural sustainability research in progress about designing an integrated interventions certification protocol for regenerating small historical centers affected by depopulation in Italy and Spain. These centers, especially in Italy, are for the most part located in less accessible *internal areas*. The Historical Small Smart City Protocol is a tool of territorial governance for municipalities. It aims to involve all stakeholders while stimulating the municipal authorities to apply to regional or European Union (EU) funds. The protocol includes “smart city” categories or priority action areas applied to historic towns and contains instructions and guidelines that explain their realization methods.

Keywords: certification systems, sustainable development, urban regeneration, cultural preservation, smart governance, minor historical centers

INTRODUCTION

In a time of slowing urban growth and suburban sprawl in several European territories, it becomes urgent to pay attention to the rehabilitation and expansion of the concept of historicity in urban peripheral areas and rural landscape (Sacchi, 2017). Instead of keeping suburbanizing and aiming at new expansion areas, one should look for existing territory elements to be conserved and ameliorated. Such a shift in attitude would avoid further land consumption and resource waste. In 1972, the European Soil Charter stressed that soil functions are essential for humankind. However, it was not until recent years that this alarm had extended into the public realm of opinion where soil consumption became a widely used term when facing the overflow of urbanization.

This perspective calls for a critical re-establishment of guiding principles in order to innovate and coordinate the actual tangle of planning tools that are no longer able to regulate the new urban development phase. Such a task is indeed difficult, especially in Italy where the environmental crisis, the lack of disaster management linked to building speculation, and the scarce attention provided by policies to these urgent issues are pushing the country to confront huge economic problems (Sylvester, 2018). On this respect, the Italian Law No. 129 on land consumption, enforced in 2013, has so far not encouraged relevant urban recovery plans that involve private investors and has been less effective than promised.

Besides the wide perception of how traditional planning tools have been insufficient to enhance urban regeneration and sustainable development, it is well known that the built heritage, unlike the natural one, is a non-renewable resource that has to be protected and enhanced (Aristone & Palazzo, 2000; Palazzo, 2017). Cultural heritage and sustainable development should be considered indissoluble in future policies because both express the logic of transmission and transgenerational solidarity. This is also necessary to ensure harmonious living conditions. Here, the debate shows a need for innovative tools (Rodwell, 2008). In particular, historical centers have a great environmental and cultural value within Italy. They can also be economically profitable, not only for the tourism industry but also for urban recovery and the reduction of land consumption (Associazione Nazionale Centri Storico-Artistici (ANCSA), 2017). Historical centers represent a very vulnerable common good that might be included in the extended concept of anthropized or cultural environment (Associazione Nazionale Centri Storico-Artistici (ANCSA), 1990).

Nowadays, historical centers are frequently located in the poorest, marginal areas of the country. They are threatened by depopulation as well as other factors that stem from an unsustainable capitalistic growth: climate change, insufficient resources, social imbalances, territorial competitiveness, and tourism pressures. All of these factors can damage the material and immaterial integrity of a small historical centers' cultural heritage. Due to the identity value of these centers and their long-lasting role in favoring and distributing the local economy across rural areas, they can and must rebalance the territory and modify the historic trends of urban concentration and metropolization (Cerasoli & Biere Arenas, 2016).

Far from traditional studies that have focused only on protection and preservation for a purely aesthetic fruition, the present research highlights the concept of "active protection" through the management and enhancement of historical small cities that are considered sources of income. This involves attributing identity value to a place that is meant to be a cultural landscape or urban ecosystem. Such an approach is inspired by the European Landscape Convention, signed in Florence on October 20, 2000, according to which the territory, and more generally the environment, begins to assume the role of resources.

For these reasons, the present research has adopted an integrated and innovative approach to the small historical city. Such an approach should be adopted in all new initiatives for sustainability because of its ability to immediately face the difficult management and cultural heritage enhancement tasks, as well as those related to environmental protection, energy saving, and economic sustainability. Its goal is to establish a shared action strategy (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), 2011; Bandarin & van Oers, 2015).

As a result, our work focused on an integrated strategy that combines heritage recovery with the strategic planning of large areas and the use of technological tools. This was done according to the procedural lines that have been identified in the Smart City conceptual framework. The goal of this study has been the development of a “smartness” certification tool: the Historical Small Smart Cities Protocol. The experimentation of the protocol is being carried out in the historical center of Sutri (Viterbo). Hopefully, it will be scaled to fit and carried out in other Italian and Spanish centers thereafter. The tool intends to leave margins for adaptation, modification, and further development in relation to local specificities.

The research began in December 2017 and will end in December 2019. The general structure of the protocol is expected to rank the smart sustainability of the smaller historical centers. Good practices and/or measures that have been carried out according to the attached guidelines are awarded bonuses that raise the score. In this way, the system encourages municipalities and local authorities to support policies and processes of sustainable urban regeneration in the small towns that were surveyed. As a projection of the future community, the “smart city” is an applicative and conceptual space defined by a set of needs and objectives that are realized through the technological innovation of different domains or fields of action, such as energy, environment, governance, mobility, and health.

The protocol’s performance criteria are set according to the recent Italian concept of the sustainable Historical Small Smart City (Cassa Depositi e Prestiti (CDP), 2013; FORUM PA, 2014). The latter includes the new action categories of “Smart Tourism” and “Cultural Heritage” within the classical European Smart City model, which is promoted by the Strategic Energy Technology Plan (SET) through the “Smart Cities and Communities” initiative (2010). The specific content of the protocol unfolded based on sustainability certification models such as the LEED Historic Building; LEED for Cities; ITACA Protocol; LEED and Italian GBC for Neighborhood Development Protocol (2009); CASBEE for Urban Development (2007); and BREEAM Communities (2012). Notwithstanding, these models completely exclude the evaluation analysis of material and immaterial cultural heritage, which is among the main contributions of the research. The protocol aims at integrating the combination of recovery with urban renewal. This is a conventional dichotomy that can be resolved through a strategy attentive to protection. At the same time, it is suitable for transforming the historical fabric, as explained in the points ahead.

Previous experiences carried out in Italy since the post-war period, especially since the ‘60s, has allowed urban planners and builders to draw up strategies for the recovery of the historical urban tissue (Giambruno, 2007). New technologies and materials for energy retrofit and renovation, done without affecting building structures and other valuable elements, now allow for updating these planning actions. Further, the introduction of technological elements such as home automation or energy saving increases their real estate value (Stara, 2014; Musetti, 2014). Besides retrofitting buildings, the categories of intervention must be integrated into a framework that implements all aspects of the Historical Small Smart City: services, connectivity, accessibility, and security, among others that are included in the protocol. They will be analyzed below.

The protocol can be an effective contribution to the field of urban studies and planning. It is a useful tool for supporting traditional plans by encouraging local entrepreneurship and creating employment in the territory. Eventually, this aims at increasing the “attractiveness” of housing, virtuous synergies, and new development opportunities.

CONTEXT OF APPLICATION AND THE STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK

Many beautiful historical centers across Italy are, like Sutri, situated in rural and marginal zones of the country. They are referred to as *internal areas* (De Vincenti, 2015). They are geographically intermediate or peripheral areas that are far from major centers and generally have less than 5,000 inhabitants. These centers are affected by depopulation, lack of services, and are frequently disconnected from the main routes of a territorial communication network. Nonetheless, they are rich in important environmental and cultural resources and quite diversified in their natural and historical anthropization processes.

During the last two decades, Italian urban migration has slowed down while the depopulation of inner areas has not. According to the 2013 ISTAT Census, 5,836 out of 8,100 minor municipalities have a population of less than 5,000. Among them, 3,651 are less than 2,000; 1,971 less than 1,000, and 845 less than 500. Overall, 10,190,451 inhabitants live in small towns. This means that 17% of the population is sparse in roughly 54% of the entire territory of Italy (Palazzo, 2017). About a quarter of the Italian population lives in the major and minor historical centers in a portion of the territory that exceeds 60% of the total and which is organized in over 4,000 municipalities (Barca, Casavola, & Lucatelli, 2014).

Demographic decline threatens the internal or peripheral areas of Spain too, according to the National Institute of Statistics (INE). Of the minor towns in Spain, 4,955 out of 8,125 have less than 1,000 inhabitants. This is mainly due to a lack of generational shift, low birth rate, and job shortage. The Spanish Federation of Municipalities and Provinces (FEMP) demands the application of “urgent State policies”. The autonomous communities (Galicia, Asturias, Castilla y León, Castilla-La Mancha, Aragón, and Extremadura) are the most affected by this phenomenon. In 2013, they organized the Forum of Regions with Demographic Challenges and were later joined by the communities of Cantabria and La Rioja (Franco, 2017). These figures, in the absence of systematic surveys on the minor urban heritage scattered throughout these countries, show a correspondence between “minor centers” and “minor historical centers” because of the lower degree of dynamism that has characterized the smaller settlements.

Other important criticalities observed in the smaller centers of the internal areas are the population aging, the loss of identity values, the lack of social inclusion for migrants, and the replacement of inhabitants. Nowadays, these are endemic and chronic phenomena (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Internal areas of Italy and the migrant phenomenon
(Image sourced by the Author AFTER ISTAT, 2016).

The international normative framework

Conserving historical urban environments while enhancing sustainable development is currently one of the most urgent and challenging political and urban planning issues. There are various well-known European and global initiatives linked to the SET Plan, such as the New Urban Agenda adopted by the General Assembly of the United Nations in 2016 and the Covenant of Majors. Difficult conditions of public finances and climate change hinder these initiatives at every level of innovation with a special focus on technology, finance for new interventions, local resources, long-term savings, and private capital. Therefore, the goal is to achieve models based on networking and partnerships for funding tangible and intangible infrastructures, social assets, and common goods through a more extensive use of institutional savings (pension funds, insurance, sovereign wealth funds, regional and national development, and multilateral banks). These partnerships are increasingly raising the attention of the EU. The creation of new financial circuits that invest savings into infrastructures and regional assets has been on the agenda of international policymakers for quite some time.

The EU has adopted a Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) for the 2014–2020 period to detect clear targets, such as raising employment and valorizing the built environment. It further supports low-carbon technologies as drivers for sustainable development. The targets are established as follows:

- Employment: at least 75% of the population between 25–64 years old to be employed;
- Research and development (R&D): 3% of the EU's GDP to be invested in R&D;
- Climate change and energy: greenhouse gas emissions 20% lower than 1990 levels, 20% of energy coming from renewable sources, 20% increase in energy efficiency;
- Education: school dropouts below 10%, at least 40% of the population ages 30–34 having completed higher education;
- Poverty and social exclusion: reduction of at least 20 million people in, or at risk of, poverty or social exclusion (EUROSTAT, 2017).

The Europe 2020 strategy is a model framework for activities in the EU on national and regional levels. The funding channels are called European Structural and Investment Funds. They are managed

by the EU countries themselves through partnership agreements. In Italy, they are received by the regions and divided into: the European Social Fund (ESF), the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD), the European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF), and the Operative Programme for Regional Development (POR), co-financed by the ESF, which both pursue the goal of inclusive, sustainable, and smart growth within a strengthened social dimension.

The national normative framework

The research follows the perspective of the Strategic Intervention Option “Internal Areas”, in line with the Partnership Agreement for the new Programming of the Community Funds 2014–2020, which has been followed by governmental initiatives such as the “National Strategy for Inner Areas” of the Territorial Cohesion Agency. This is a strategic financing plan on the regional level that, in the framework of the National Reformation Plan (*Piano Nazionale di Riforma*, PNR), is aimed at combating the demographic reduction and relaunching the development and services of these areas through ordinary funds of the Stability Law and through the Community funds available for all the regions of the country over the 7-year period of 2014–2020. The plan has been published by the Senate of the Republic of Italy: 17th Legislature – Research Service, Dossier No. 240, 10 Vol. II (12/15/2017, 2:57 p.m.).

The strategy aims to join the services of municipalities in the territory through the Union of Municipalities tool and “experiment” interventions of regeneration that comply with the communities. If effective, those interventions will be permanent. Then, coordinated intervention programs must be provided to ensure the protection of landscape and architectural beauty. These are among the goals that, in the long run, the present research will hopefully achieve. The design and validation of the Historical Small Smart City Protocol can be part of this framework and contribute to creating a new strategy to be spread throughout every region and macro-region of the country. While enhancing the recovery of small historical centers, the protocol can create new jobs, achieve social inclusion, and reduce the cost of land abandonment. Such a scenario is relevant especially because urban planning instruments and conservation laws have often proven to be at odds with environmental protection, sustainable development, and urban regeneration. The fact that the Protocol is also based on participative processes should further highlight its crucial priority to decrease territorial vulnerability (Pica, 2018).

The Union of Municipalities is an institutional form of association between town governments, as specified by the Constitutional Court ruling No. 50/2015. It is ruled by the Legislative Decree No. 267, August 18, 2000, which implements the No. 265 law from August 3, 1999, especially Article 32. It consists of two or more municipalities for the joint operation of functions or services within the municipal jurisdiction. The union has statutory autonomy within the principles established by the Constitution and by the community, State, and regional norms.

The present research takes into account the various “government memories” that compose the planning and legislation experiences of Italy. This, in order to understand the current situation and analyze how an integrated new strategy can find a useful and effective inclusion in compliance with the current planning tools and regulatory constraints (Ministerial Decree No. 1444/1968 on Planning and Urban Design Standards; Law No. 457/1978 on the Decennial Plan for Residential Buildings and Recovery Plans; Consolidated Text of the Laws: Presidential Decree No. 380/2001, and subsequently upgraded versions; Decree *Scia2*: Legislative Decree No. 222/2016; and the Code of Cultural Heritage: Legislative Decree No. 42/2004).

On this basis, a new viewpoint should broaden the Italian concept of “A” zone (i.e. the protected historical center, disconnected from the rest of the city in progressive transformation) to the entire

consolidated city, strictly in contact with its naturalistic environment and its inhabitants (Ruocco, 2015). Moreover, according to the new regional laws, municipalities are now encouraged to individualize areas of urban regeneration through the Urban Regeneration Programmes (PRU) for promoting widespread interventions that involve new private investments (Reg. Law No. 7/2017 of Lazio; Reg. Law No. 6/2009; Reg. Law No. 24/2017 of Emilia Romagna, and Reg. Law No. 12/2008 of Umbria).

This transition to urban renewal in Italy has the merit of streamlining administrative practices with the transformation of strict prescriptions of municipal planning tools. This trend follows and improves the Italian tradition of complex programs but with high risk, putting the interests of the community in the background while favoring private investors. In Europe and in Italy, the term urban regeneration is associated with integrated actions aimed at addressing the vicious circle between physical degradation and social exclusion, which are at the basis of worsening inequalities in the contemporary city. Nevertheless, the concept of urban regeneration implicit in the regional laws, including one of the most advanced such as that of Emilia Romagna, seems to ignore such a fact.

It is therefore essential to speak up about the management of common goods and the assessment of the social and environmental impacts of operations over the largest urban ecosystem. The construction of the protocol of integrated interventions for the recovery and the smart and sustainable development of small historical cities are going to follow a specific and strategic methodological approach that starts from these premises of ensuring a balance between social, economic, physical, and environmental elements.

PROTOCOL CONTENT AND ACTIONS

Based on the considerations introduced in the previous section and in relation to the real global sustainability of the first urban regeneration operations that are underway, it is beneficial to make further clarifications. Such clarifications are necessary to define the content and actions of the protocol.

The protocol includes the conceptual framework of the urban regeneration not seen as a sum of sporadic interventions but as a coordinated path based on economic and social feasibility with a view towards environmental sustainability. The revival of local economies and the building sector should go hand in hand with the historical centers' recovery and modulated protection. It is fundamental to integrate the public and the private initiatives. New technologies can play a key role at this point. They improve the communication network and the effectiveness of interventions, moreover for energy saving.

At the bottom of this urban regeneration concept lies a fundamental principle, sharing globally the objectives that guarantee a valid usability of public spaces and sustainable transformations. Moreover, to be effective, urban regeneration must produce an attractive image of the city or of the small municipality and its territory.

The Protocol Certification System can certainly support the creation of an integrated strategy that allows for assessing the social, environmental, and global impacts of the operations. It offers strategic lines in form of tables with intervention fields and sub-indices. These indicate the precise actions to be undertaken. An incremental score will be given to each action according to the level of quality, complexity, and cost of its performance. The protocol is "smart" because it contains a guideline document that indicates the procedures for carrying out the planned interventions. A third category of content can be found in a database using GIS (Geographic Information System) software, which

will support the publication of open source data for the creation of an online observatory of the historical center of Sutri (Viterbo). This is to stimulate participation and the raising of citizens' awareness about the themes of urban regeneration. This database will also serve to define quantitative and qualitative indicators for the evaluation of possible and foreseeable scenarios based on the various proposed interventions.

The bonus allocation criterion is based on an accomplishment for at least one of the subsections of each intervention area. The score augments according to the complexity of the operations. The realization of further interventions envisaged in the action categories will allow for higher qualifications that will also guarantee better rankings for the Regional Funding Bids if the protocol is adopted by national policies.

The protocol's strategic framework

As mentioned, the Historical Small Smart City concept is at the base of the protocol's strategy. Of note is the history of the Italian architecture and environmental research that has led to such an outline. In the 60s, the architect Saverio Muratori formulated the importance of investigating how a historical place could be renewed without being betrayed. According to Muratori, a place has resilient structures, lines of force, which must and can be maintained or regenerated through a dynamic process (Berruti, 2013, p. 32). Therefore, one must think about an eco-friendly and resilient habitat with its bioclimatic potential and structural resilience that is stratified and consolidated over time (Appendino, 2016; Salat, 2011).

The protocol's procedures also aim at valorizing the Cultural Historic Environment (Osservatorio Nazionale per la Qualità del Paesaggio, 2018). This is a conceptual framework that includes the Historical Small Smart City within a network of its territory. This perspective assumes the quality of the landscape as the foundation of the strategic scenario for the development of Italy. This great opportunity stands out in the contemporary, globalized world. Institutions and politics should provide this to their citizens for answering the demand of life quality and environments capable of contributing to individual and collective well-being.

The construction process of the Protocol Strategic Framework is being carried out on the basis of a SWOT analysis, integrating different aspects of the actual conditions of Sutri and other Italian and European minor centers. The strategy is oriented at the enhancement of opportunities and lines of force, taking in account critical aspects and threats (Fig. 2).

The strategic framework is technically grounded on a long-term and elastic strategic management plan. As for the Lazio region, it foresees that the Recovery Plans could be flanked by operational tools like the protocol and other instruments included in its guidelines that optimize interventions on both the executive and economic level. The project management approach of this framework prioritizes the interventions. The priority goes from the most immediate and easy actions to the most difficult, following the analysis of the operative, economic, and highly critical issues. This order starts with setting up synchronous actions in the short term, then develops action plans in the mid to long term.

With regard to funding and economic feasibility of the integrated interventions, the framework includes several compound reward measures, such as the reduction of building permit fees; the increase in volumetry outside the historical center's perimeter; simplified paperwork for change of intended use; tax reduction, and better loan conditions. It is important that the long-term aid is granted in a context of sustainable development so that partners and institutions do not invest money only for it to be exhausted. Each institution should participate in the wider system of control and scrutiny with their own budgets.

STRENGTHS		WEAKNESSES	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - HISTORIC BUILDINGS - "HUMAN SCALE" - COMPACT FORM - LOCAL TRADITIONS - ENVIRONMENTAL QUALITIES - BIOCLIMATIC DEVICES - HISTORIC OR RECENT INFRASTRUCTURES 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ABANDONED BUILDINGS - VEHICULAR MOBILITY - URBAN INSECURITY - SOCIAL IMBALANCE - SCARCE PUBLIC SERVICES - LACK OF ACCESSIBILITY - LACK OF TOURISTIC ROUTES 	
OPPORTUNITIES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LATENT TERRITORIAL CAPITAL - ENHANCE TELEWORKING - NATURAL RESOURCES - ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY - KNOW-HOW EXCHANGE - REUSE OF EXISTING INFRASTRUCTURES 	THREATS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - INCREASING ABANDONMENT - SUBSTITUTION OF TRADITIONAL INHABITANTS - INCREASING UNEMPLOYMENT - INCREASING SOCIAL COSTS - INCREASING INSECURITY

Figure 2. SWOT matrix with the current, principal characteristics of minor historical centers in the internal areas of Italy.

This strategy encourages the Union of Municipalities, which is the institutional form that allows municipalities to enter into preferential rankings for access to EU and national funding. Thus, the union has a leverage effect. This is why actions undertaken within a union are awarded more bonuses. Among them: Sustainable Mobility Plans (PUMS); Urban Regeneration Programmes (PRU), and Action Plans for Sustainable Energy (PAES). A municipality alone is less effective, and its actions can perform only basic scores. The best rankings can be achieved only within a union. This is because the most rewarded interventions and planning actions can be sustainable and feasible through this tool.

The protocol's integrated interventions

The safeguard of collective interests and mitigation of negative market effects have to be taken into consideration. There are risks of demolition and replacement of valuable buildings, and of gentrification of historical centers. Hence, the necessity that the various initiatives are part of an overall strategy. They must improve the physical urban environment (i.e., building fabric inside and outside the historical center) and affect all the areas of action that we have defined for the Historical Small Smart City: mobility, economy, environment, heritage, living, and governance (Fig. 3).

Concerning the "Mobility" activities area, each municipality can operate without adhering to a Union on the graduation of interventions on the use of public space in the short, medium, and long run (maximum 5 years). This kind of action consists of the installation of restricted traffic areas with temporarily allowed access for residents only, no parking in public spaces, and special parking permits for disabled people. No parking measure can be put into force gradually, according to the realization of new parking in the belt areas outside of the city walls or the historic center's perimeter. At the same time, without any Union, the municipality can secure pedestrian routes and open connection spaces. More complex projects must be realized within a network of municipalities. These are the smart and sustainable mobility interventions such as bike sharing; new electric minibuses to connect with major railway stations; improvement of routes and timetables for intermodal transport; new interchange nodes, and traffic monitoring.

Figure 3. The six action areas of the Historical Small Smart Cities Protocol with interventions.

Regarding the “Economy” activity area, incentives introduced by the regional laws for urban regeneration are maintained while local public-private partnerships are encouraged. The abandonment of buildings in small municipalities is addressed through loans for temporary uses and the reconversion of brownfield sites, as well as other tools. The reduction of energy consumption is a crucial part of this category of actions, moreover for the economic return and the monetary recovery of the cost of the operations. Smart tourism is included, ranging from regulation and containment of widespread hotels to the application of regulations on commercial activities in the historical center. The promotion of new tourist routes, incentives for tour operators, and support for e-tourism are also provided.

The “Environment” activity area focuses on the maintenance and restoration of biodiversity; conservation of wetlands and bodies of water; enhancement of rural uses (especially of peri-urban farmlands); prevention of areas subject to flooding; and protection and securing of steep slopes. All these are basic activities that can be realized outside of the Union of Municipalities. The actions connected to the employment of smart facilities, such as smart grids and monitoring of incinerators, are more complex and require the union participation.

The “Heritage” activity area envisages measures and objectives to protect the inhabitants of areas where regeneration programs are enforced. It avoids their removal, supports social housing and social *mixité*, and determines criteria for the insertion of variations in the base areas of available housing with tax credits and other economic incentives that involve owners or small private investors. In addition, housing conditions are expected to be improved through the “modulation of protection”. This involves a series of operations applied to residential built heritage (minor construction with testimonial value) where specific guidelines support virtuous and rigorous interventions, especially in the case of restoration and conservative rehabilitation or building renovation. These interventions are based on precise GIS analysis of the building fabric, which guarantees the development of an interoperable, shareable, and quickly updatable database, as well as the optimization of the management and control of the procedures. All the interventions are targeted at the safeguard of the original types and elements, most of the time eliminating the recently added or deteriorated elements.

The “modulation of the protection” is a procedure already included in the technical standards for implementation (NTA) of the Recovery Plan for the historical center of Formello (Cerasoli, 2010). The novelty here is in its use for a pilot project centered on a minor historical center of a peripheral area and not of a metropolitan belt. Further, it works with a GIS database and is linked to energy retrofit and domotics.

The types of intervention range from restoration and conservative rehabilitation to building repositioning. They follow a cataloging work and in-depth analysis of the characters and types of existing built heritage, which allow for the classification of building categories. Each category will correspond to a type of intervention, passing from the most restrictive and protective, such as for monuments, to the most transformative. The “Living” and “Governance” areas envisage professional training and promotion of employment through services and infrastructures. They follow the guidelines attached to the protocol in the form of a dossier for urban participation. Bottom-up participation is not an exercise of democracy for obtaining consensus, but rather an essential factor for guaranteeing the effectiveness of regeneration programs. This adds to the correct use of public resources for solving needs without wasting money or incurring undesired interventions.

The protocol guidelines document can be downloaded for free from the project web page via the ESRI Open Source platform. Based on the ArcGIS Online service, the protocol is provided by the LabGIS at Roma Tre University in support of our research group.

IMPLEMENTING PROTOCOL ARRANGEMENTS

The sustainable development conceptual model of the Historical Small Smart Cities Protocol is network oriented. It favors the Union of Municipalities and promotes inclusive planning tools, such as the General Urban Plan (PUG) in Emilia Romagna or the collective Recovery Plans used by the Union of Municipalities of the Romagna Forlivese (SUSREG, 2015).

The protocol would reconnect the broken relations between small historical cities and their territory. New development strategies centered on the networks of municipalities (following a multi-polar system) and the complex identity of the historical places would follow. Moreover, the protocol would include the use of new digital communication technologies; the possibility of interchanging data and activating streamline and business communications, and the capability to use local renewable sources. These factors could make life in smaller historical centers affordable for a greater number of people.

The importance of protecting the cultural heritage within its specific landscape needs to be recalled. Nonetheless, this should not be in conflict with the possibility of reflecting on culture from a “smart” perspective, in order to individualize milestones and opportunities for relaunching and sustainably regenerating places (Cerasoli & Biere Arenas, 2016, p. 297). Thus, this research focuses on the network between smaller centers as a preliminary platform for structuring an internal area and, subsequently, the need to “activate” the individual nodes of the network.

In the internal areas, the nodes of the network are primarily the historical centers of minor municipalities long-marked by abandonment, socio-economic crisis, and structural decay. At the same time, the consolidated policies have shown their limits in dealing with the historical center as separate from the rest of the municipal territory, usually classified as an “A” area and to be referred to in the Recovery Plan.

On the national level, the dynamics of transformation in the mid to long term confirms a geography modulated on different forms of center-periphery relationships. These are made more complex by anthropological and socio-economic factors, yet are still marked by the unification of services even on the primary level. A supra-municipal scale exists *de facto* due to the drastic downsizing of welfare. Such processes will be accentuated in the future. Corrections that can be activated nationally on the policy level are thus required (Palazzo, 2017).

A recent survey by the Ministry of Economic Development focused on these subjects. It integrated the condition of “proximity” in terms of travel times between each municipality and the nearest major centers with a pre-established level of health, education, and infrastructure (Ministry of Economic Development, 2013). The document classifies “Service offering centers” (sometimes called “poles”) as those municipalities or aggregations of municipalities that can provide all the secondary school services, hospitals with emergency rooms, and railway stations. This thematic reading, in association with the demographic trends that have affected minor municipalities over a period of forty years, allows for identifying the importance and value of autonomous trajectories of territorial development in synergy with policy and instrumentation at the regional level: sector planning, extensive area planning, and special planning (Palazzo, 2017).

The possibility of relaunching the minor centers as “poles” can realistically be enforced according to specific situations. For example, possibilities would be different in proximity to major cities or when promoting inter-municipal federations as cooperation (like the Union of Municipalities) for one possible integration of the urban type: municipalities do not own the full range of services but each develops a particular “utility” and all are mutually accessible. Within this framework, the requalification and recovery of disused buildings and abandoned areas can contribute to the activation of new poles of socio-economic aggregation (through reconversion of abandoned or free assets). These factors could implement the local market supply chains.

The GIS system supports the optimization of both the protocol’s content and actions, as well as its implementing arrangements. Hopefully, it is going to be a Decision Support System (DSS), a tool that can enhance and guide the decision-making processes. The databank is going to allow the calculation of specific indicators for the evaluation of future scenarios. The general indicators chosen could make this system implementable and extendable to the national and European territory. This tool could be useful for the management and monitoring processes of small historical centers and their surrounding territory. The main indicators of the system are being drafted by taking into account the recent reports and studies by the Italian Superior Institute for Environmental Protection and Research (ISPRA) and its partners. These works aim at providing national indicators of vulnerability within the MASTER ADAPT project (Giordano, 2017). These indicators are linked to the recent GIS system realized by the Region of Lazio and others to describe the rural Italian mountain areas within the Geographic System of the Mountains of Lazio (SGML) project (Regione Lazio, 2009).

Other indicators related to the built heritage and the morphologic characteristics of minor historical centers are also being set up in order to define indices of transformability, urban quality, and solar energy productivity (Iannilli & Petroselli, 2016). The main problems for the protocol’s application could be related to the governance system of the municipalities whose 5-year mandate is too short compared to multi-year planning. Moreover, many municipalities do not know yet the potential for application of the new regional law directives for urban regeneration.

On the operational level, it could be necessary to enroll local non-municipal institutions into partnerships and agreements with local and voluntary associations (such as the local action groups, GAL) or the involvement of local authorities such as the regional and national parks managed by

administrative bodies such as Pro-Loco, Mountain Communities, and Provinces. On an economic level, it may be useful to create shared local investment funds to be controlled by other local authorities and maintained over the years. For this reason, it is important to activate long-term partnerships with individual entrepreneurs, business networks, local farmers, manufacturers, and consortia.

CONCLUSION

The framework of integrated interventions supported by the Historical Small Smart Cities Protocol can be applied as a support tool for territorial governance, municipalities, and local authorities in an incremental, multi-scalar, and multidisciplinary perspective. Overall, it is possible to foresee that the main chronic, critical issues (weak economies, demographic aging, loss of identity values, and lack of social inclusion for migrants) would be mitigated through the measures introduced by the Protocol, such as the integration of different kinds of broad actions. This would strengthen the short supply chain and the local production with the result of making migrants' employment and training flourish. The activation of municipal agreements supporting telework, the improvement of basic assistance services, and the creation of participatory design processes with the strengthening of cultural events all run in the same direction. More specifically, these measures aim at enhancing the residential attractiveness of the smallest historical centers of the inner areas by improving the quality of life they have to offer.

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